

How does Investment in Green Stocks Compare with Traditional Stocks on Indian Equity Market : An Empirical Investigation

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Abstract : *The present study makes an attempt to examine the performance of green stocks represented by ESG index against traditional stocks in Indian Stock Market for the period April 1, 2017-March 31, 2023. Whereas ESG Nifty 100 Index is a proxy for green stocks, for traditional investing we consider broader index, NSE Nifty 500. The paper initially analysed the risk-return profile of the two indices followed by co-integration analysis to understand the association between the two. The result of the study fail to detect any long run co-movement amongst the two indices with results being consistent for three different co-integration techniques. Bi-directional causality was however visible. The risk-return assessment revealed that the conventional index ; NSE 500 index was giving similar return as that of ESG 100 index but with lower risk thereby showing that ESG index has not delivered as expected inspite of index including Companies scoring high on ESG parameters.*

Keywords : ESG Nifty, Nifty 500, Co-integration, Causality, Risk-Return Profile.

1. Introduction

The choice of selection of a stock of a Company is a function of a number of factors and one such factor which has gained importance amongst the investing community during recent past is the company's adherence to principles of environment, society and governance or simply, the ESG principles. Again, ESG which has a synonym as 'sustainability' is very closely related to some other terms often used in research studies like responsible investing, green investing, thematic investing, socially responsible investing and so on. However, the million

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dollar question which arises in an investor's mind is; If a Company focuses on ESG principles and also makes substantive investment thereof, then will such an investment pay off as compared to traditional investing or in simple words; Does it really pay to be sustainable?

Investors today often talk of 'ESG alpha' an alpha built up after considering ESG Principles as against standard 'alpha' which is independent of such 'restrictions'. When we speak of 'restrictions' under ESG, these are usually defined in exclusions model of ESG and aims at restricting investments in companies involved in arms, tobacco, human rights, climate change violations, gambling, adult content and private prisons. On the other hand, instead of restricting investments, investing in firms which provide solutions to environmental problems is another ESG model called 'Impact Investment Model'. The model became popular after the release of Sustainability Accounting Standards in 2018 and many indices in US and other parts of the world now have started following the 'Impact Investment Model' (Ouchen, 2022).

One of the popular research dimensions with respect to ESG investing has been to undertake a comparative assessment of ESG performance with conventional stocks or indices and here the broad conclusion is that ESG is not a miracle tablet which can be swallowed to achieve both targeted return and risk. Thus as the research has proved, even the best of the ESG scores, do not translate to best of the returns (Kanamura, 2022 ; Broadstock et al., 2020; Brunet, 2019; Giese and Lee, 2019). A study by Cornell, (2021) found that investments in ESG assets may be somewhat beneficial for corporates as they are able to raise capital at lower costs associated with green technologies, however for an investor this benefit to the Company actually gets translated to lower expected returns therefore adversely impacting the risk-adjusted performance. Similarly, a study carried out by Atz, et al., (2023) analysed 1100 research papers on ESG investing published between 2015-2020 and their findings revealed that ESG investing was not giving a 'return' which was superior to traditional stock investing. Their own viewpoint after analysing these research studies was that not only classification of ESG investing was still ambiguous, but both investors and researchers need to explore beyond the financial angle of ESG with respect to how sustainable strategies could be meaningful differentiators.

Going ahead, empirical research on ESG has actually gained momentum during the last few years and researchers are trying to understand the drivers of ESG and how the same can be integrated and adopted in business so that benefit of the same is accrued to all the stake holders viz, Company, Public, Society,

Government and Investors. Amongst the dimensions explored, the most popular area is making a comparative analysis with existing conventional indices with respect to 'return' and 'volatility of returns'. We now discuss some of the existing research studies on ESG investing along with their empirical findings.

Moosawi and Segerhammar, (2022) applied two models; AR(1)-GARCH(p,q) model and a Diebold-Yilmaz spillover approaches to understand the return and volatility spillover between ESG Indices and traditional benchmark indices including most financial assets. The results revealed that a country's ESG specific index was more integrated with another country's ESG index rather than other financial assets. However they also noticed that there was an evidence of both 'return' and 'volatility' transmission from country specific index to all other financial assets. On the other hand, an attempt was made by Cornell (2021) in his study to understand the theoretical basis for investing in ESG both by corporates and investors. He concluded that investors going with a sole purpose of 'returns' are likely to be dissatisfied with ESG investments, however if return per se was not a big issue but their preference for ESG was in providing benefit to society, company and environment, then the investor according to their analysis appeared to be satisfied. He further argued that even if one assumes that a 'risk premium' is attached to an ESG stock, then Companies with high ESG ratings are usually assumed as ones which are exposed to lower risk which simply means that such companies actually provide lower and not higher expected 'returns' to investors. In yet another study, Auer and Schuhmacher (2016) tried to compare ESG investments made in US, Asia-Pacific region and Europe and found that ESG selected stocks did not fair better than any kind of passive investing in stocks. In Europe, the study also found that investors did tend to pay a price for their socially responsible investments while in Asia Pacific or US markets, ESG investment did provide 'returns' compatible with broader markets.

On the other hand, there has however been different viewpoint regarding 'volatility of returns' pertaining to ESG investing. A study by Ashwin Kumar et al., (2016) applying traditional ratio analysis tools; Sharpe and Treynor on 157 firms listed on Dow Jones Sustainability index found that ESG brings in lower 'volatility' which immediately gets translated to higher risk adjusted returns. Another group of researchers could find reduction in 'return volatility' but only for a particular sustainability index and not for other sustainability indices e.g. a study carried out by Hoang, et al., (2021) on 344 listed firms on Eurostoxx index during 2019-20 where they divided the firms on the basis of high and low ESC Performance with rating being provided by two sources: MSCI ESG rating

and Sustainalytics ESG Risk Rating. The results showed that firms which received high ESG rating from MSCI had a lower 'volatility' performance spread, but the same was not the case with Sustainalytics ESG Risk Rating where there was no difference in volatility spread for the two type of firms. Furthermore, MSCI ESG rating clearly showed that firms with high ESG performance were able to resist better to all types of shocks viz. market capitalization shocks, news impact, stock beta shocks and so on.

Further, considering that the available data on ESG has its limitation of being recent origin, new models are being experimented and applied on this evolving research area thereby offering tremendous research potential. Furthermore, investment figures have clearly revealed that in spite of not having any special advantage in financial terms, investor's interest in this promising area has not come down but on the contrary has grown exponentially over the last few years e.g. US Markets showed a rise in investment flows into ESG funds from 5 billion US \$ in 2018 to more than 50 billion US \$ in 2020, a rise of ten times in two year time period (Morningstar, 2021).

Also, being a research interest of recent origin, a lot of the studies on ESG investing have also focused on ESG performance during the crisis periods especially covering extensively the two major crisis; Global Financial Crisis of 2008 and Covid Pandemic of 2019. The results obtained from these studies have been somewhat mixed ; whereas researchers like Das et al. (2018) could see resilience in ESG investing during 2008 Global Financial Crisis, others like Folger-Laronde, et al., (2022) found the opposite or almost negligible resilience during the Covid 19 period. Most studies have actually found that ESG investing provides no extra gain to investors in terms of 'financial return' nor does this type of investment works as a 'hedge' or a 'safe haven' like gold during crisis periods and hence have requested State to provide some incentive for this all important theme to flourish. Thus in the absence of any suitable incentive, investors have now started viewing investing in ESG stocks as a disincentive to sustainability (Folger-Laronde, et al., 2022).

On the other hand, if we keep aside the 'return' aspect, then some researchers have found that during the crisis periods, ESG funds do provide relief in terms of slightly lower 'volatility' than the conventional indices. A study by Mousa, et al., (2021) assessed pre and post Covid 19 volatility scenario on two stock indices; Arab's S&P Composite index and S&P ESG Arab Index by applying GARCH and NARDL approaches. The findings revealed that during pre-Covid period, volatilities of both the indices were equally affected however post-COVID

period saw substantial lower magnitude of volatility in the ESG index as compared to conventional index with shocks in ESG index dying out quickly as compared to conventional index. On the other hand, all the researchers do not agree that the ESG indices are more resilient during crisis and this was seen in a study by Ouchen (2022) where the researcher considered a special ESG index "MSCI USA ESG Select", an index of companies with high ESG scores across sectors and conventional index "S&P 500.", the objective being to compare the turbulence of both indices for which they applied "GARCH and EGARCH" models and their single regime switch modifications viz. Markov-switching "GARCH and EGARCH". The results showed that ESG index was non-linear however the index showed signs of lower 'volatility' only after a rise and not after a fall in 'returns'. Furthermore, ESG index was less resilient to crisis situations than conventional portfolio. Then almost similar results were obtained by Folger-Laronde et al., (2022) where they tried to explain in terms of 'financial returns', the sustainability performance of ETFs during the Covid 19 pandemic and found that it was no way less resilient to market downturn during the crisis period. Their study thus identified two challenges with respect to measurement of sustainability performance and these include, first identifying the right indicators for responsiveness during a crisis, and second, the transparency in ESG rating methodology. Yet another study focusing on Covid-19 pandemic was carried out by Demers et al., (2021) where they showed that ESG did not provide any resilience during COVID-19 pandemic, and therefore questioned the generalizability of CSR being resilient during Global Financial Crisis be extended to ESG in times of Covid-19 as done by some researchers. Further, their research clearly showed that investors who invested on the basis of higher ESG scores during the Covid-19 did not get superior returns.

Questions have also been raised by various stakeholders regarding methodology adopted by ESG indices and also transparency of their operations (Chatterji, et al. 2009). Kanamura (2022) in his study showed that environmental values were not adequately demonstrated by ESG indexes, while social and governance values were reflected to some extent. They also found that over a period of time the performance of ESG indices tends to converge to conventional indices. Similarly, La Torre et al., (2020) revealed that ESG Index's contribution in explaining stock return was very limited with results of individual companies varying considerably, the possible reasons according to them could be other factors influencing the stocks 'return' or that the relation between could be nonlinear. However after pooling, the researchers could find "ESG index" was impacting 'stock returns' in a somewhat positive manner. Then Ashwin Kumar

et al., (2016) found that different sector industries reacted differently to ESG and therefore clubbing together of all industries into single unit by ESG funds must be avoided.

Some researchers and investors however do believe that companies incorporating sustainability in their operations shall surely give superior performance in 'returns' in the long run even if the same may not be visible as of today. A few researchers have also tried to link other financial variables to ESG and one such study was carried out by Gökmenođlu and Mentep (2023) where they tried to establish a relation between crude, natural gas, and gold with two stock indices; one being conventional popular index; Dow Jones Industrial Average and second the sustainability index; Dow Jones Sustainability World Index. The cointegration results from the two indices differed considerably with respect to speed of adjustment towards equilibrium which was faster @8.4% for DJIA while it was 3.3% for sustainability index. Further the long run impact of crude on both indices was negative while for gold this was positive. On the other hand, natural gas impact was seen only on one index i.e. sustainability index. Causality was seen moving from crude to conventional DJIA index unidirectionally while this was bidirectional with respect to sustainability index.

Sustainability Index was also considered using GARCH approach in a study by Sariannidis et al., (2010) where they found not much difference between a broader index and sustainability index in terms of crude's impact on these two market indices. A study by Nakajima et al., (2021) showed evidence of return spillover from crude to US and European Market ESG indices. Again, Maraqa and Bein, (2020) investigated linkages between traditional stock indices of crude importing and crude exporting countries, two sustainability stock indices (Dow Jones sustainability World Index and Dow Jones Sustainability Europe index) and crude oil. The results showed that sustainability indices had higher interaction with crude importing countries, while crude exporting ones had higher correlation with simple crude return which became even more stronger after global financial crisis. Significant 'volatility' transmission was also seen amongst all the three variables.

Moving further, the focus of the present study is on ESG Nifty Index of India which has been developed on lines of other existing sustainability indices across the world. The ESG Nifty Index excludes companies involved in the business of alcohol, tobacco, controversial weapons and gambling. It also excludes companies which had any ESG controversy in the past and weight of each Company in the index, is based upon its market cap and ESG Scores.

Furthermore, compared to some of the advanced economies where ESG concept has been for a while, ESG concept in relatively new in India with the country's first ESG Index being launched in April, 2011 while its counterpart, Dow Jones Sustainability World Index was launched on 8th Sept. 1999, 12 years before it was launched in India. Thus, for India the concept being only ten years old, needs an extra boost which can come mainly from institutional investors and stock market watchdog, SEBI.

Thus, in spite of being a recent origin, the study has tried to build by including two stock indices viz. ESG Nifty Index of India and S&P Nifty 500 for their co-integrated movement in the long run. The data for the present study collected is daily closing prices of two stock indices; ESG Nifty Index of India and S&P Nifty 500 for the six period April 1, 2017-March 31, 2023.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 explains the methodology employed, Section 3 provides empirical results and discussion on these results, Section 4 provides conclusion and study implications, followed by two more sections, Section 5 for references followed by Section 6, Appendices.

2. Methodology

The methodology employed under the present study includes developing two models; a co-integration and a causality model. For testing long run co-integration between S&P Nifty 500 and ESG Nifty Index of India we have applied three co-integration techniques; Phillips-Ouliaris (1990), Engle Granger (1987) and Johansen (1998) models; whereas the first two models Phillips-Ouliaris (1990) and Engle Granger (1987) are commonly employed for two variable co-integration, the third model Johansen (1998) technique gives results of co-integration which are considered highly reliable under most situations. For testing causality we have applied traditional VAR based Granger Causality (1969) Procedure. All the models developed have been pretested by applying Model Diagnostics of Serial Correlation, Heteroscedasticity and Stationarity of Variables.

2.1. Developing a Co-integration Model

One of the main objectives of our study is to determine whether, the two indices viz. NSE Nifty 500 or the conventional index and ESG Nifty Index exhibit a long run stable co-movement. Many financial variables which show inconsistent behaviour in the short run, do end up with a stable and more predictable co-movement in the long run and whether the same is also true for our variables has been tested in our study by applying three different co-integration

techniques. All the three techniques employed for co-integration analysis have some distinct characteristics and hence the conclusions drawn after analysing these techniques would help us in arriving a correct assessment of the co-movement of the variables. Whereas Johansen Model (1998) is a popular technique which employs an MLE Procedure for parameter estimation, Engle Granger (1987) and Phillips-Ouliaris (1990) are two step OLS procedures and carry out the co-integration test through residuals.

2.1.1. Engle Granger Co-integration Method (1987)

Engle Granger is a two-step co-integration test procedure is also popularly called the test of residuals. The test carries out co-integration assessment by first generating residuals from eq. (i) and then applying unit root ADF test on these residuals as given under eq. (ii). Null Hypothesis (Ho): No Co-integration or Non Stationarity of Residuals.

$$y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 x_t + u_t \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

$$\Delta u_t = \gamma_2 u_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_{3,i} \Delta u_{t-1} + e_t \dots\dots\dots(ii)$$

2.1.2. Phillips-Ouliaris Co-integration Model (1990)

Phillips-Ouliaris is also a two-step test procedure, and generates residuals in a similar manner as Engle Granger Method, however the generated residuals follow unaugmented Dickey Fuller regression as shown under eq. (iii). Null Hypothesis under Phillips-Ouliaris shall again be Non-Stationarity of Residuals.

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \mu + Y_{i(t-k)} \dots\dots\dots(iii)$$

From eq. (iii), long run one sided residual variance is computed by applying the

$$\text{formula} = \frac{\text{Residual Variance}}{(1 - \text{sum of lagged diff residual coefficients})^2}$$

Both residual variance and long run one sided residual variance as computed above, are used to obtain 'z' statistics results to test for co-integration.

2.1.3. Johansen Co-integration Model (1998)

The third co-integration model applied in our study is Johansen (1998), a VAR based Co-integration test which may be stated as $\Delta Y_{i,t} = \mu + \delta Y_{i(t-k)} + \sum_{L=1}^{k-1} \pi_{i,L} \Delta Y_{t-L}$,

where 'i' is the ith variable, 'k' is the max no. of lags following lag SC structure which for long run relation remains same for all the independent variables. On the other hand, for short run relation, for each independent variable these can range from 1 to k-1, all being included in the model. The model develops 'δ' where 'δ' represents a matrix of coefficients signifying long term relation amongst the variables and is the fundamental matrix of the co-integration.

$$\text{i.e., '}\delta\text{' = } \begin{pmatrix} T_{11i} & T_{12i} & T_{1ni} \\ T_{11i} & \dots & \vdots \\ T_{m1i} & \dots & T_{n,mi} \end{pmatrix}$$

If matrix does not have full rank then the matrix can be factorized as $-\delta = \alpha\beta$, where 'β' contains the cointegrating vectors and 'α' signifies the adjustment parameters. For co-integration we focus on the rank of the matrix 'δ' as all the vectors need not be co-integrated. If there is no co-integration, Matrix has a rank '0', if only one cointegration exists then rank is '1' and so on. Further, if co-integration is detected we proceed towards computation of characteristic roots and eigen values. The different variants we consider in our study include Model I : No Deterministic trend but with intercept, Model II : Linear Deterministic trend but no intercept and Model III : Linear Deterministic trend but with intercept.

2.2. Developing a Causality Model

We develop a Causality (Granger 1969) Model (eq.iv and v), where model shown as eq. (iv) is restricted while the same given as eq.(v) is unrestricted . We compute residual sum of the squares of two models and check for causality using the following 'F' formula

$$ESG_t = \theta_1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_{i,L} \beta_i ESG_{t-1} + u_{1t} \dots\dots\dots(\text{iv})$$

$$ESG_t = \rho_1 + \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j ESG_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_j NSE 500_{t-1} + u_{2t} \dots\dots\dots(\text{v})$$

$$F_{\text{Wald}} = \frac{(RSS_{\text{res}} - RSS_{\text{unres}}) / m}{RSS_{\text{unres}} / n - m}, \text{ If } F_{\text{Wald}} > F_{5\% \text{ table}} \text{ we reject the Null Hypothesis}$$

(Where RSS: Residual Sum of the Squares, 'm' is the number of parameters to be estimated, 'n' being no. of observations, no. of lags are decided by SC criteria)

The hypothesis under causality is developed as under :

$H_{01} : (i=1,2,3,\dots,n)$ Causality is not flowing from to ESG.

$H_{A1} : (i=1,2,3,\dots,n)$ Causality is flowing from to ESG

3. Results of the Study

Under this section we discuss the study results, the tabular format of the same is given in Appendices. Appendix I shows the statistical data description of two Indices namely, NSE Nifty 500 Index and Nifty ESG 100 Index over a period of six-years starting from April 1, 2017, to March 31, 2023. The data based on daily closing prices of these two variables have been collected from the www.nseindia.com and these have been transformed to daily spot returns by

applying the formula : $\ln \left(\frac{P_t}{P_{t-1}} \right)$ where P_t is the closing price of the index at day

't' and P_{t-1} is the closing price of the same index at day 't-1'. The computation of returns from closing prices facilitates the comparison of the two indices across different parameters as shown in the Table 1. This table provides information about the four moments over the study period on yearly and aggregate basis, i.e., Mean, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. It also provides additional information on Coefficient of Variation (C.V) and Normality test for the two variables.

The analysis reveals that the mean return for the combined study period is almost same for both the indices i.e., 0.0004, however the flagship broader index; Nifty 500 gives higher return for two years 2017-18 and 2018-19 as compared to its counterpart; Nifty ESG 100 index. It is interesting to note that 2017-18 was year of negative returns in stock market and the likely reason being the impact of currency demonetisation which was declared by the Indian government on Nov. 8, 2016. Again, the stock returns were negative and were in line with most global stock indices during 2020-21 due to the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on markets.

ESG Index for India has performed better in terms of average return than Nifty 500 index for four of the six years for which the study was carried out viz. 2019-20, 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23. Further, even though ESG includes companies which have thrust on environment, social or corporate governance issues, the same is not reflected in terms of risk as the Standard Deviation for daily returns for the entire study period is again slightly higher than Nifty 500 Index. This reveals that investors in ESG Index have to contend with a risk element which

is no different from Nifty 500 stock index while on the contrary NSE 500 index is slightly lower in terms of risk than ESG 100 index for the six year period of study. The picture is almost the same if we consider this on yearly basis and NSE 500 index has lower standard deviation as compared to ESG index for four of the six years included in the study.

If we adjust return for risk, we obtain a level picture i.e. out of six years, three years have CV of NSE 500 as lower while for rest, it is ESG Index with lower CV. CV for the aggregate period 2017-23 is lower for ESG 100, however the difference is not substantial. Thus, the broad conclusion drawn is that the ESG investing has failed to create much enthusiasm amongst Indian investors as compared to some of the other advanced countries where investors are willing to even sacrifice some of the returns for ESG investing which usually gets reflected in terms of reduction in risk in these indices.

The study also carried out distribution characteristics for the two indices and it was seen that both the distributions were negatively skewed for all the years except for the year 2019-20. Also both distributions were not normally distributed

which was confirmed by JB Normality test : $JB = \frac{n}{6} \left\{ S^2 + \frac{1}{4}(K - 3)^2 \right\}$; 'n' being the number of observations, 'S' is the Skewness and 'K' Kurtosis of the distribution.

The next set of results pertain to long run co-integration between NSE 500 and ESG 100 indices for which we had applied three different models viz. Johansen Co-integration Model (1998), Phillips-Ouliaris (1990) and Engle Granger (1987). For Johansen Co-integration Model (1998), the study has used three variants and the results of all the three variants is given in Appendix II. All the three variants viz. Model I : No deterministic trend but with intercept, Model II : Linear deterministic trend but no intercept and Model III : Linear deterministic trend with intercept accept the Null of No Cointegration as the 'p' values of both trace and eigen value test statistics exceeds 0.05 in all the three cases. Similar results of No Cointegration is also observed from other two co-integration tests; Phillips-Ouliaris (1990) and Engle Granger (1987); the results of the same are shown in Appendix III. Appendix III gives information on two different statistics; 'tau' statistics and 'Z' Statistics and their corresponding probabilities. The results however reveal no co-integration between Nifty 500 and Nifty ESG indices .

After having seen that no long run co-movement exists amongst these two indices, we decided to check for short run results for which we carried out

Granger Causality (1969) tests, the results of the same are given as Appendix IV. The results reveal that the causality is bi-directional and both NSE 500 and ESG Index are impacting each other in the short run.

In our final results section, we present the result of our Model Diagnostics (Appendix V) where we have carried out three types of tests; stationarity, serial correlation and heteroscedasticity. For stationarity we have applied unit root ADF while for Serial Correlation and heteroscedasticity, the tests employed are 'Q' Statistics and BPG Heteroscedasticity test. The results of Diagnostics are given in Appendix V and these results reveal that all model diagnostics are fully satisfied.

4. Conclusion and Implications

To conclude, the present study made an attempt to examine the performance of investment in green stocks as compared to the traditional stocks in the Indian financial markets. To achieve this objective, a statistical analysis of the Nifty ESG 100 index and S & P Nifty 500 index was carried out, the purpose being to identify the interlinkages and causality between the two indices.

The study first examined the risk-return profile of the two indices, and later developed three co-integration models; Phillips-Ouliaris (1990), Engle Granger (1987) and Johansen (1998) to understand their characteristics and dynamic movements of their interlinkages. It was seen that both NSE 500 and ESG indices were giving similar return, however NSE 500 was doing so with lower risk thereby showing that ESG index has failed to deliver in spite of index including Companies which scored high on ESG grounds.

With respect to long run co-integration, the study however failed to identify the same between the two indices. On the other hand, short run bi-directional causality was seen whereby the two indices were seen impacting each other. No long run relation amongst the indices gives a clear signal that investors can keep both the assets in their portfolio if their time horizon is long run, however investors should also not expect miracles with this portfolio as risk profile of both assets is quite similar. On the other hand, the results of short run causality is bidirectional which implies that one variable could be used to obtain information on another. Thus all the results combined together simply reveal that market in India is still not mature enough to consider ESG as a separate category and hence requires the necessary boost which has to come mainly from policy makers duly supported by institutional investors and retail to some extent.

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6. Appendices

Appendix I : Statistical Description of Variables: NSE Nifty 500 Index and Nifty ESG 100 Index														
	NIFTY 500 INDEX CLOSE PRICE						Nifty ESG 100 INDEX CLOSE PRICE							
	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	Combined 2017-23	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	Combined 2017-23
Mean	-0.0001	0.0008	0.0022	-0.0013	0.0003	0.0004	0.0004	-0.0003	0.0007	0.0023	-0.0011	0.0006	0.0005	0.0004
Std. Dev.	0.0093	0.01010	0.0130	0.0169	0.0081	0.0067	0.0112	0.0095	0.0098	0.0134	0.0170	0.0081	0.0064	0.0113
(C.V.) = σ / μ	-92.6	12.625	5.909	-12.9166	24.782	15.238	27.873	-28.757	13.568	5.9362	-15.0860	13.4105	13.4841	25.9563
Skewness	-0.1881	-1.2299	-0.0086	-2.6953	-0.1794	-0.6155	-1.7747	-0.1416	-1.1132	0.3858	-2.4099	-0.2895	-0.4612	-1.4706
Kurtosis	3.5948	7.2439	7.8954	23.8141	3.4832	4.0245	24.7138	3.3885	6.9948	10.1149	22.4320	3.4443	3.5867	24.4213
Jarque- Bera	5.1392	248.6355	248.6411	4757.693	3.7430	26.29123	29993.16	2.3978	216.1288	531.3847	4125.239	5.5029	12.2478	28966.80
JB(Prob)	0.0766	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.1539	0.000002	0.000000	0.3015	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0638	0.0022	0.0000
Obser.	249	248	249	247	248	246	1487	249	248	249	247	248	246	1487

Appendix II: Co-integration results using Johansen Methodology

Null Hypothesis	Model I : <i>No Deterministic trend but with intercept</i>		Model II : <i>Linear Deterministic trend but no intercept</i>		Model III : <i>Linear Deterministic trend with intercept</i>	
	Prob(Trace)	Prob (Max Eigen)	Prob(Trace)	Prob (Max Eigen)	Prob(Trace)	Prob (Max Eigen)
No Cointegration exists	0.2521	0.3144	0.1332	0.2922	0.7413	0.6877
One cointegration	0.3630	0.3630	0.0577	0.0577	0.7979	0.7979

Appendix III : Co-integration results using Phillips-Ouliaris and Engle Granger Methods

Dependent	Engle-Granger Cointegration Test				Phillips Ouliaris Cointegration Test			
	tau-Statistics	Prob.	Z-Statistics	Prob.	tau-Statistics	Prob.	Z-Statistics	Prob.
ESG Index	0.216195	0.9994	0.651209	0.9995	0.256452	0.9995	0.762666	0.9996
Nifty 500	0.354714	0.9997	0.957265	0.9997	0.277833	0.9997	0.768717	0.9996

Appendix IV : Causality Results

Null Hypothesis	Observations	'F'(Computed)	Probability	Result
ESG Index does not cause Nifty 500	1547	3.84888	0.0215	Null Rejected; ESG Index→Nifty 500
Nifty 500 does not cause ESG Index	1547	3.62037	0.0270	Null Rejected; Nifty 500→ESG Index

Note : SC Criteria used for lag determination , No. of lags=2

Appendix V: Model Diagnostics					
# Stationarity test : ADF Unit root test		ESG Nifty Index		NSE Nifty 500 Index	
Null : Non Stationary/Presence of Unit root		Level	1 st Diff	Level	1 st Diff
1. Coefficient 'p' values	1	0.2966	<0.01	0.2078	<0.01
2. Table result Null (Accepted/Rejected)	2	-4.1328 (Accepted)	-39.3744 (Rejected)	-4.2996 (Accepted)	-38.3753 (Rejected)
Critical Value at 5% for ADF Unit Root -4.8598					
*BPG Heteroscedasticity test					
1. Observed R ²	1	0.551132			
2. Probability χ^2	2	0.4579			
** Serial Correlation: 'Q' Statistics					
Lag 1		'Q' Statistics 1.3625 'p' value 0.243			
Lag 5		'Q' Statistics 3.1979 'p' value 0.525			
<p>Note 1. $\Delta Y_{v,t} = \beta_{1,v} + (\beta_{2,v} - 1)Y_{v,t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_{3i,v} \Delta Y_{v,t-i} + u_{v,t}$; (v=1,2) 'v' denote variable; NSE 500 or ESG 100, $Y_{v,t-1}$ reveals the stationarity of variable 'v' and has $(\beta_{2,v} - 1)$ as its coefficient, $u_{v,t}$ is the random error term. Null: Non Stationary time series.</p> <p>2 * BPG Heteroscedasticity test: We run the regression, obtain the residuals and then develop an auxiliary equation. $u_t^2 = \partial_1 + \partial_2 X_{2t} + \partial_3 X_{3t} + \dots + \partial_k X_{kt}, \dots$; Null being Homoscedasticity and B.P.G test follows Chi Square Distribution i.e. $n.R^2_{aux} \sim \chi^2_{m-1}$</p> <p>3. ** Serial correlation , second diagnostic and has been tested by using 'Q' Statistics where we define; $Q_m = n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^m \rho_{u_i,t}^2$; 'Q_m' $\sim \chi^2$ distribution with 'm' d_f (no. of lags). Null(H₀) for the same being $\rho_{u_{1t}} = \rho_{u_{2t}} = \dots = \rho_{u_{mt}} = 0$ and alternative hypothesis being some of the $\rho_{u_{it}}$ are not equal to 0. We further define $\rho_{u_{1t}} = \frac{cov(u_t, u_{t-1})}{\sqrt{var(u_{t-1}) var(u_t)}}$, and the study provides information about serial correlation at lag 1 and lag 5</p>					